

Readiness to Adoption Digital Technology for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in Indonesia

Penny Rahmawaty

Lecturer, Department of Management, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Email: penny_rahmawaty@uny.ac.id

 ORCID:

Abstract

The readiness of MSMEs in Indonesia to adopt digital technology is a tough challenge during the Covid-19 pandemic. The successful use of technology depends on the acceptance and use of each individual wearer. This study aims to determine user attitudes in adopting digital technology which are influenced by performance expectations, expectations of efforts made, facilitation conditions, and social influences. In addition, attitudes towards digitalization will affect the intention to use digital technology in MSMEs. In addition, anxiety and worry factors in using digital technology will strengthen or weaken attitudes towards the adoption of digital technology.

The population in this study is MSME entrepreneurs in Indonesia with a sample frame of MSME entrepreneurs who have used digitalization in their business operations. The number of samples used was 150 MSME entrepreneurs in the Yogyakarta region and Central Java.

The results showed that performance expectations and business expectations did not affect the attitude toward adopting digital technology. Meanwhile, facilitation conditions and social influences have a significant positive effect on attitudes towards digital technology. The attitude of adopting digital technology has a significant positive effect on the intention to use digital technology. The attitude of adopting technology does not mediate the influence of performance expectations, business expectations, facilitation conditions, and social influences on the intention to use digital technology. Similarly, anxiety does not moderate the influence of performance expectations, business expectations, facilitation conditions, and social influences on attitudes toward adopting digital technology. So, this study cannot prove mediating attitudes to adopting digital technology and moderating anxiety on the influence of performance expectations, business expectations, facilitation conditions, and social influences on the intention to adopt digital technology.

Keyword: *digital technology, attitude, anxiety, intention to use*